

CEO Characteristics and Audit Quality of Listed Firms in Nigeria: The Moderating Role of Audit Committee Gender Diversity

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Abstract

This study examined moderating role of audit committee gender diversity on interaction of CEO characteristics and audit quality of listed firms in Nigeria. The study used a sample of 94 out of a population of 156 firms using their secondary data and employed panel regression and logistic panel regression analysis. The result showed that CEO Ownership interaction with audit fees is not significant. However, it is positive and significant with audit firm size. CEO tenure interaction with audit committee gender has negative moderating effect on audit fees while exhibiting positive effect on audit firm size. The study concluded that gender diversity in audit committee will reduce CEO tenure and CEO ownership effect on audit quality of listed firms in Nigeria. The study then recommends among others that listed firms in Nigeria should be required to have gender-diverse audit committees, as this has shown to improve governance ethics and promote higher audit quality. This could be achieved through stringent corporate governance policies and listing requirements by stock exchanges, particularly the Nigeria Exchange.

Keywords: Audit quality, CEO characteristics, Audit Committee Gender, Audit Fees.

JEL: M41, M47, M48

1. Introduction

Audit reports are important fund providers, stakeholders, investors and stakeholders to make informed decisions on which firm to channel their funds without fear of incurring loss. These audit reports are expected to have accurate and reliable financial information that will be the bedrock of their decisions and this information is expected to come from the top management. Businesses such as Satyam Company in India and Tyco Kozlowski Company in the United States have regulations intended to restrain CEOs and company management from declaring liquidation due to financial manipulations. Thus, justifying investors' mistrust of CEOs (Dachomo & Bala; 2020). (Qawasmeh & Azzam, 2020, Chen et al, 2021. Hendricks et al, 2022). Also profit-manipulation practices have increased in the last decade in both advanced and developing nations (Dachomo & Bala, 2020; Oradi et al., 2020). Hu et al. (2015) also opined that longer tenure and greater CEO shares holding aids this practice. Hou et al. (2017) and Borgi et al. (2021) opined that CEO tenure is contentious.

CEOs are expected to supervise accounting process to boost stakeholders trust on financial report (Ali & Zhang, 2015; Du et al., 2017; Shen, 2021) (Uyioghosa, 2019) as they impact firm's audit quality (Arif et al. 2022, Li & Cai, 2022) through share ownership that helps them pressure auditors to overlook some financial irregularities or approve reports that

are not accurate or complete (Payne & Williamson, 2021). In Nigeria, Moody's 2018 report revealed that Diamond bank failure was caused by excessive use of power by their CEO (Moody, 2018). Also, power tussle among top executives of First Bank of Nigeria Holding due to shares ownership was recently reported by the media including the Economy post, 2024.

Prior studies established direct link between CEO characteristic and audit quality (Garcia-Blandona, et al., 2023; Borgia, et al., 2021; Saidu & Aifuwa, 2020), (Arif, et al., 2022; Chao, 2022; Song et al., 2022; Payne & Williamson 2021)). Also, Obazee and Amede (2019), financial sectors; and Mustapha, et al. (2021) non-financial sector excluded audit fees and audit firm's size they did not identify critical mechanisms that could strengthen and enhance this interaction. Alawaqleh et al (2021) recommended the inclusion of moderating variable. This study explored other variables and identified audit committee gender seen as a catalyst for quality audit Olowookere et al ((2021) as moderating component. Since a gender-diversity enhances audit process (Li et al, 2022; Miglani & Ahmed, 2019). Therefore, the objective of this study is to examine CEO characteristics and audit quality of listed firms in Nigeria: the moderating role of audit committee gender for a period of 2013 to 2022.

2. Literature review

2.1 Conceptual review

2.1.1 Audit Quality

Definition of AQ as market-assessed joint probability that a given auditor will both (a) discover a breach in the client's accounting system, and (b) report the breach, (Deangelo, 1981), resonates with this study. Resolve to disclose identified breach is a gauge of an auditor's objectivity towards a client (DeAngelo, 1981, p. 186). Gaynor, Kelton, Mercer, and Yohn (2016) assert that improved audit quality is an assurance that financial reports accurately reflect firm's position. According to Hubais, et al, (2022), quality audit is one that has no errors or frauds and was completed with a high degree of integrity and accuracy (Salehi, Moradi & Paiydarmanesh, 2017). This study defines audit quality as audit report possessing standards and attributes that boost investors' confidence on firms' financial reports and assures them of accuracy of information they purpose to base their investments decisions on. Audit quality in this discuss is represented by audit fees and the big 4 audit firms which are specific attributes (Defond, et al, 2014). Audit fees refer to money given by firms for audit services usually based on the complexity of the exercise and auditors level of expertise, goodwill etc. It is professional consideration for audit services (Sukrismo, 2012) and this definition suffices for this study. The big four audit here refers to firms rated as the biggest four in terms of size, expertise, staff, technical knowhow etc.

2.1.1.1 The Chief Executive Officer (CEO) Characteristics

CEO characteristics are attributes that distinguish the CEO from every other staff. And for this study they are CEO ownership and tenure. Early proponents of business environment and management theory like Peter Drucker (1943) viewed CEO as occupying top echelon of a firm. Julia Thompson, (2024) asserts that a CEO must be one with traits that can be emulated by low level managers and employees. CEO share holding and ownership is a board decision connected to leadership compensation, acceptance and appointments done in line with Agency Motivation Alignment Theory to ensure and maintain goal congruency with all interest groups. (Mitnick 1973, Jensen and Meckling (1976), Laher and Proffitt (2020). CEO tenure on the other hand is the length of time a CEO stayed an organisation (weisbuch, 1991).

2.2 Theoretical Review

Agency theory pioneer (Berle & Means, 1932) and strengthened by (Jensen & Meckling, 1976) is the anchor theory for this study as it provides for principal-agent–firm diverse conflict of interest as it infers that conflicts of interest arise between a company's management, CEO, and its external stakeholders, such as shareholders and auditors.

2.3 Empirical Review

CEO ownership and Audit Quality conflicts in their influence as literatures support the notion that CEO ownership reduces audit quality. Cao, et al. (2020) examined CEO ownership and audit quality in China, using 2,259 firm-year observations from 2010 to 2016. The authors employed regression analysis and discovered that higher CEO ownership leads to lower audit quality. Also, Kim and Yun (2020) investigated CEO ownership and audit quality in Korea, using 4,828 firm-year observations 2010 to 2016 using regression analysis. From results, CEO ownership negatively affects audit quality.

Dhaliwal, et al. (2019) also studied CEO ownership and audit quality in United States, using 10,582 observations from 2000 to 2013. The authors used regression analysis while controlling for firm size, leverage, profitability, etc. The results indicated that higher CEO ownership causes lower audit quality. Piccoli and Bianchi (2020) also investigated CEO ownership, auditor choice, and audit quality in Italy, using 819 firm-year observations from 2010 to 2016. From the result, higher CEO ownership is associated to choosing a non-Big 4 auditor, which in turn relates to reduced audit quality. These studies were for different periods, used different study variables and methodology different from this current research

Mitra et al. (2020) studied audit fees and CEO tenure in the USA. From a population of 170,081 from 2000 to 2013, the study employed 15,925 observations. Using regression analysis, they discovered that audit fees are greater in the first three years of a CEO's employment, which suggests that early-career CEOs exhibit high-risk conduct which raises the possibility of financial mis-reporting. In China, Cai et al. (2022) looked into the connection between audit pricing and previous chief executive officer. They used regression analysis to discover that former CEOs have negative effects on firm's audit fees. The study came to the conclusion that directors lower operating risks, enhance earnings, and lower audit fees in the organisations. Chao (2022) investigated CEO traits and how succession planning affects audit fees. 445 firm-year data from 89 US listed companies with CEO turnover between 2012 and 2016 made up the sample. The analyses used panel data models. The findings showed high fees for businesses that have new CEO. Kalelkar and Xu in (2021) using sample of 11,198 firms from 2007 to 2016, and with ordinary least squares regression model examined the impact of the middle and long stages of executives' employment on audit fees. They noted that audit fees are significantly lower when executives move into the medium to long tenure stages. Since this study is American based, expanding such research to other nations, like Nigeria, may give a different result.

Li and Cai, (2022) also examined CEO power through CEO and CFO's tenure consistency on audit pricing. They found that having a CEO and CFO with the same tenure increases company's cost. Ashafoke, et al, (2021) also examined CEO traits and accuracy of financial reports of listed 15 financial organisations in Nigerian from 2008 to 2019. It derived conclusions from the upper echelon theory. Panel regression technique was used to analyse the study data which showed a positive and significant correlation. Alawaqleh, et al. (2021) using 325 manufacturing firms listed on Amman Stock Exchange 2014 to 2018 with logistic regression, discovered insignificant correlation between CEO tenure and independent directors with audit quality. They concluded that CEO tenure has no bearing on audit quality. Again, this study falls back in terms of time lag and the variable, domain and

geography are different from those of this study.

Fasua, et al (2020) from their study concluded that listed Nigerian cement companies audit quality is improved by audit committee. Pucheta-Martinez, et al. (2019) looked into AC gender diversity and audit fees in French firms included in the SBF 120 stock market index between 2002 and 2017 employing system GMM estimate approach, panel sample of 97 firms and 1,488 firm-year observations. They discovered that having women on ACs increase efficiency of board oversight. However, these studies were subjected on domains different from those for this study. Based on the gaps identified, the following hypotheses were formulated to help achieve specific study objectives:

- H₀₁: CEO ownership does not affect audit quality of listed firms in Nigeria.
- H₀₂: CEO tenure does not affect audit quality listed firms in Nigeria.
- H₀₃: Audit committee gender has no moderating effect on CEO ownership and audit quality of listed firms in Nigeria.
- H₀₄: Audit committee gender has no moderating effect on CEO tenure and audit quality of listed firms in Nigeria.

3. Methodology

Ex-post facto research design is employed by this study based on its nature and peculiarity with model specification build up that supports the empirical testing capturing the study objectives earlier stated with multivariate analyses done to eliminate bias that can potentially invalidate tests results. The study population consist of all 156 listed Nigeria firms in operation from January 2013 to December 2022. A sample size of 94 firms was selected from this population such that all sectors have opportunity of fair representation using Random sampling technique and data analyzed using STATA. The econometric model specification is presented thus:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{AUDF}_{it} &= \alpha_{it} + \beta_1\text{CEOW}_{it} + \beta_2\text{CEOT}_{it} + \beta_3\text{FSZ}_{it} + \beta_4\text{ROA}_{it} + \beta_5\text{FAG}_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots 1 \\
 \text{AUFE}_{it} &= \alpha_{it} + \beta_1\text{CEOW}_{it} + \beta_2\text{CEOT}_{it} + \beta_3\text{ACG}_{it} + \beta_4\text{CEOW*ACG}_{it} + \beta_5\text{CEOT*ACG}_{it} + \\
 &\beta_6\text{FSZ}_{it} \quad \quad \quad + \quad \quad \quad \beta_7\text{ROA}_{it} \quad \quad \quad + \quad \quad \quad \beta_8\text{FAG}_{it} \\
 &+ \varepsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots \\
 \text{BIG4}_{it} &= \alpha_{it} + \beta_1\text{CEOW}_{it} + \beta_2\text{CEOT}_{it} + \beta_3\text{FSZ}_{it} + \beta_4\text{ROA}_{it} + \beta_5\text{FAG}_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots 3 \\
 \text{BIG4}_{it} &= \alpha_{it} + \beta_1\text{CEOW}_{it} + \beta_2\text{CEOT}_{it} + \beta_3\text{ACG}_{it} + \beta_4\text{CEOW*ACG}_{it} + \beta_5\text{CEOT*ACG}_{it} + \\
 &\beta_6\text{FSZ}_{it} \quad \quad \quad + \quad \quad \quad \beta_7\text{ROA}_{it} \quad \quad \quad + \quad \quad \quad \beta_8\text{FAG}_{it} \\
 &+ \varepsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots 4
 \end{aligned}$$

Where, AUDE, is audit fee, BIG4, audit firm size, CEOW, CEO ownership, CEOT, CEO tenure, FSZ, firm size, ROA, return on asset, FAG, firm age. It, panel data (company and time), α , constant $\beta_1 - \beta_8$, are coefficients of parameter estimates, e, error term

Table 1:
Variables, definitions and Measurements

Variable Name	Acronym	Variable Type	Variable Measurement	Source
Audit Firm Size	BIG4	Dependent	To be measured 1 for Big 4 and 0 for non-Big 4	Alsmadi(2021),
Audit Fees	AUDF	Dependent	The logarithm of total audit fee (in N) in year t.	Omar (2023)
CEO Ownership	CEOW	Independent		
CEO Tenure	CEOW	Independent	if CEO tenure more than 3 years 1 less than 0	Nikbakht et al. (2022)
Audit committee gender	ACG	Moderating	Equitable representation of both male and female genders n the committee	Olowookere et al. (2021)
Firm size	FSZ	Control	Natural log of total assets	Shakhatreh and Alsmadi (2021)
Return on asset	ROA	Control	Earnings after tax/total asset	Shakhatreh and Alsmadi (2021)
Firm age	FAG	Control	Number of years in the Nigerian exchange	Shakhatreh and Alsmadi (2021)

Source: Authors' Compilation (2024)

4. Data Analysis and Discussion of Finding

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 2:
Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Obs	Mean	Std.Dev	Min	Max
AUDF	940	4.401	0.652	2.6	7.07
BIG4	940	0.638	0.481	0	1
CEOW	940	2.90	9.071	0	63.68
CEOT	940	0.589	0.492	0	1
ACG	940	0.142	0.169	0	1
FSZ	940	24.348	2.14	19.57	30.339
ROA	940	0.021	0.129	-1.325	1.762
FAG	940	39.87	20.013	1	101

Source: Authors' Computation (2024)

Descriptive statistics reveal CEO characteristics, audit quality, and control variables for Nigerian listed firms. The average audit fee is 4.40, with low variation (SD = 0.65). About 64% use Big 4 auditors. CEO ownership averages 2.90%, with a wide deviation (SD = 9.07%). Most CEOs (59%) have tenure >3 years. Only 14% of audit committees include women. Firm size averages 24.35 (SD = 2.14), with ROA at 0.02, indicating modest profitability. Firm age averages 39.87 years (SD = 20.01), reflecting both long-established and newer firms in Nigeria's market.

Pearson Correlation Matrix

Pearson correlation matrix is shown in Table 3. Among independent variables, CEO tenure and audit committee gender shows weak correlations with other variables, while CEOWACG has a moderate correlation with CEOW (0.5248), although less than 0.80 indicating no multicollinearity.

Table 3
Correlation Analysis

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)
AUDF	1.000									
BIG4	0.553	1.000								
CEOW	-	-	1.000							
CEOT	0.353	0.265								
ACG	-0.115	-0.111	0.235	1.000						
CEOWACG	0.085	0.140	-	0.016	1.000					
CEOTACG	-	-	0.064	0.150	0.193	1.000				
FSZ	0.170	0.057	0.525	0.482	0.676	0.288	1.000			
ROA	0.034	0.010	0.039	0.482	0.676	0.288	1.000			
FAG	0.920	0.435	-	-	0.081	-	0.041	1.000		
			0.301	0.087		0.145				
	0.079	0.068	-	0.001	-	-	0.002	0.093	1.000	
			0.078		0.003	0.089				
	-	0.074	-	0.025	0.138	-	0.108	-	-0.59	1.000
	0.106		0.120			0.060	0.147			

Source: Authors' Computation (2024)

4.2 Result of Robustness Tests

Robustness tests are carried out to test validity of statistical inference of both the linear regression (audit fees) and logistic regression (BIG4) models.

4.2.1 Multicollinearity Test

Table 4
Multicollinearity Test

VARIABLES	VIF	1/VIF
CEOW	1.65	0.607
CEOT	1.80	0.554
ACG	2.41	0.415
CEOWACQ	1.57	0.636
CEOTACQ	3.28	0.305
FSZ	1.16	0.863
ROA	1.02	0.981
FAG	1.09	0.921
Mean	1.75	

Source: Authors' Computation (2024)

The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values indicate low multicollinearity among the variables, as all VIFs are below 10. The highest VIF (3.28) is for CEOTACQ, suggesting some moderate correlation with other variables, while lowest is (1.02) for ROA, indicating minimal collinearity. The mean VIF is 1.75, confirming low multicollinearity overall. The variance inflation factor (VIF) values show a low multicollinearity among the variables with a below 10 value across (3.28 for highest and 1.02 for lowest). This suggests a moderate to minimal collinearity.

Table 5
Diagnostic Tests

Tests	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Normality	- (0.000)	- (0.000)	- (0.000)	- (0.000)
Heteroscedacity	331.09 (0.000)	337.44 (0.000)	24.51 (0.000)	26.44 (0.000)
Auto correlation	22.491 (0.000)	23.54 (0.000)		
Hausman test	65.33 (0.000)	65.23 (0.000)		
Hosmer-Lemeshow goodness of fit	-	-	75.75 (0.890)	95.12 (0.391)

Source: Authors' Computation (2024)

Table 5 presents diagnostic test results for models assessing correlation between audit quality and CEO characteristics. Normality test p-values (0.000) reject the null hypothesis, indicating non-normal distribution of residuals. Breusch-Pagan test showed significant heteroscedasticity ($p = 0.000$), suggesting that error term variance is not constant, which may affect regression efficiency. Autocorrelation tests for Models (1) and (2) show significant values ($p = 0.000$), indicating serial correlation in the error terms, requiring robust standard error corrections like Driscoll-Kraay. The p-values (0.000) in both models suggest that a fixed effects model is more appropriate than a random effects model. For the BIG4 model, logistic regressions (Models 3 and 4) yield non-significant p-values (0.890 and 0.391), indicating a good fit for predicting outcomes. Despite heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation concerns, robust logistic regression was used in the analysis.

Table 6
Robust Fixed effect and Robust Logistic Regressions

	Robust FE (1)	Audit Fees Robust FE (2)	Robust Logit (3)	BIG4 Robust Logit (4)
CEOW	-0.000 (0.226)	-0.000 (0.292)	-0.031 (0.004) *	-0.104 (0.000) *
CEOT	-0.0005 (0.437)	-0.002 (0.046) *	-0.241 (0.139)	0.244 (0.273)
ACG		0.016 (0.021) *		3.18 (0.003) *
CEOW*ACG		-0.001 (0.726)		0.390 (0.000) *
CEOT*ACG		0.007 (0.001) *		-3.867 (0.002) *
FSZ	0.009 (0.000) *	0.009 (0.000) *	0.579 (0.000) *	0.568 (0.000) *
ROA	-0.008 (0.004) *	-0.009 (0.002) *	0.383 (0.638)	0.451 (0.492)
FAG	0.005 (0.052)	0.005 (0.040) *	0.522 (0.000) *	0.503 (0.000) *
R-sq within/Pseudo R2	0.271	0.276	0.202	0.232
F-stat/Wald-st	1031.90 (0.000) *	1665.21 (0.000) *	163.36 (0.000) *	170.41 (0.000) *

Note: P-value in parentheses * $p < 0.05$

Source: Authors' Computation (2024)

The F-statistic for both models is significant ($p = 0.0000$), indicating good fit. Model 2 (interaction model) has a slightly higher R-squared (0.2760), suggesting better explanation of audit fee variability. For BIG4 models, pseudo R² is 0.202, with Model 4 showing an improvement to 0.2318.

4.3 Discussion of Findings

Table 6 shows that CEO ownership (CEOW) has a negative and insignificant effect on audit fees (coefficient = -0.000, $p = 0.226$), suggesting no influence on audit quality in these firms, contrary to Piccoli and Bianchi (2020). However, from audit firm size model, CEOW is negatively associated with Big 4 auditor supporting agency theory and aligning with prior studies by Piccoli and Bianchi (2020), Kim and Yun (2020), and Cao et al. (2020). Table 6 showed that in the direct model, CEO tenure has negative significant effect on audit quality measures (coefficient = -0.005, $p = 0.437$) for audit fees; and (coefficient = -0.241, $p = 0.139$) for big 4. This implies that CEO tenure does not influence audit quality of these Nigeria firms. This finding contradicts Almasria, et al. (2021), Mustapha, et al. (2021) and Kalelkar and Xu (2021).

Table 6 showed interaction between CEO ownership and audit committee gender on audit fees is negative and insignificant (-0.000662, $p = 0.726$) in Model 2, indicating no meaningful combined effect. However, the interaction on BIG4 (coefficient = 0.390, $p = 0.000$ in Model 4) is positive and statistically significant. This suggests that gender-diverse audit committee mitigates negative influence of CEO ownership on Big 4 auditor. Gender diversity acts as a moderator, reducing the controlling tendencies of CEO-owners. This is in line with prior studies by Nekhili et al. (2019).

The interaction between CEO tenure and audit committee gender is positively significant (coef = 0.007, $p = 0.001$), indicating that gender-diverse audit committees moderate CEO tenure and audit fees suggesting that longer tenures and gender diversity lead to higher audit fees. Gender-diverse committees increase oversight encouraging firms to pay for higher-quality audits. This is in conformity with Abbasi (2019) who discovered favourable correlation between female directors on audit committees and the quality of the audit. However, in Model 4, the interaction between CEO tenure and audit committee gender is negatively associated with hiring a Big 4 auditor (coeff. = -3.867, $p = 0.002$). This suggests that while longer CEO tenures may lead to a preference for lower audit quality, gender diversity on the audit committee does not significantly mitigate this trend as gender diversity alone may not counteract entrenched CEO behaviours.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examined audit committee gender moderating role on CEO characteristics and audit quality of listed firms in Nigeria using data from 2013 to 2022. Robust fixed effect regression and logistic panel regression tools were employed for data analysis. Findings showed that CEO Ownership interaction with audit fees and firm size is insignificant and positive. CEO tenure interaction with audit committee gender has negative moderating effect on audit fees and positive effect on audit firm size. The study concludes in tune with parameters used and within the chosen time frame that a more gender diverse audit committee weakens the negative influence of CEO tenure and CEO ownership on audit quality of listed firms in Nigeria.

Based on these results, this study hereby makes the following recommendations: Nigerian firms should establish CEO tenure policies to ensure fresh perspectives, accountability, and reduce complacency. Shorter tenures of between 5-10 years, promote improved audit engagement and investor confidence, with consequences for policy

violations; Nigerian firms should implement gender-diverse audit committees to enhance business ethics, governance, and audit quality. Corporate governance codes or exchange listing requirements, like those by NGX, can help achieve this; and Regulatory bodies like SEC, Financial Reporting Council, and NGX should mandate gender-diverse audit committees. Setting minimum female representation targets would drive change in boardroom dynamics, supporting improved practices and ethics.

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